

The White Dwarf Population in Our Solar Neighborhood

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Our understanding of white dwarfs has dramatically increased over the last decade. At the same time, new questions have emerged. Thanks to missions like Gaia, we now have high-precision photometry and astrometry for nearly 200,000 of these objects, with low resolution spectra available for about half of them. Being the most common stellar remnants and having precise evolutionary models available, white dwarfs serve as stellar chronometers. An initial analysis of a complete sample within 100 pc (~10,000 objects) reveals a low binary fraction ($f_b=0.32$) and traces of galactic evolution in kinematics and the star formation rate, with a peak ~2.5 Gyr ago.

The population of white dwarfs and main-sequence stars

Observed Gaia 100 pc sample

Population synthesis sample

Global densities and relative fractions are in good agreement between simulations and observations

- We can model it in general terms, but finer details need improvement
- A population synthesis fitting of the Gaia resolved white dwarf binary population [1], i.e. $DWD^1=1.18\%$ and $WDMS^2=6.31\%$, leads to:
 $f(a) \propto a^{-1}$, $n(q) \propto q^{n_q}$, with $n_q = -1.13^{+0.12}_{-0.10}$ and $f_b = 0.32 \pm 0.02$.
- Besides, a fitting of the unresolved WDMS population found in Gaia [2] leads to an estimate of the common envelope efficiency of α_{CE} in [0.12,0.37] [3]
- ¹ Double degenerate white dwarf, ² White dwarf + main-sequence binary system

Kinematics of the white dwarf population

Spatial distribution of WDs in the solar neighborhood during several orbit integration [4]

- Stars within the Solar neighborhood disperse within a short time compared to the Galactic orbital period of the Sun.
- Statistical study of L_z and orbital E of the Solar neighborhood. Disk components perform nearly circular orbits while halo WD display a larger variety of energies and momenta.

The star formation rate

- Using a Random Forest algorithm, the population of WD DA within 100 pc from Gaia has been identified.[5]
- From the analysis of the color-magnitude diagram and the photometric age estimation we can derive the star formation history.
- A clear peak of formation appears between 2-3 Gyr

References

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